

CERIS-ULB DIPLOMATIC SCHOOL OF BRUSSELS
UNIVERSITÉ LIBRE DE BRUXELLES-ULB

EXECUTIVE MASTER IN INTERNATIONAL POLITICS

Navigating the Crime-Terror Nexus

An analysis on the factors, mechanisms, and state impacts

Randa KANDROUCH

Under the supervision of: Professor Tanguy STRUYE DE SWIELANDE

Academic year 2023-2024
Exam session September 2024

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Summary

The thesis investigates the complex relationship between terrorism and organized crime, known as the crime-terror nexus. Traditionally seen as distinct entities, these phenomena have progressively converged, with terrorist and criminal groups collaborating and adopting each other's methods to achieve their goals. This nexus can be explained by globalization and weak or poorly governed states.

The study analyses factors contributing to the crime-terror nexus, focusing on three key areas: financing of terrorism through criminal activities, the transfer of skills between criminal and terrorist groups, and the role of weak states. A qualitative mixed-methods approach was employed, combining a systematic literature review with four expert interviews. The literature review critically examined academic and governmental sources, while expert interviews provided additional insights. The primary research question is: "What are the factors contributing to the crime-terror nexus?" This is further divided into three subsidiary questions addressing the above-mentioned factors for a comprehensive analysis.

The study finds that as state sponsorship for terrorism has declined, terrorist groups have increasingly relied on criminal activities for funding. This mutually beneficial relationship allows criminal organizations to exploit the instability caused by terrorism. The flexibility of terrorist groups to exploit local criminal opportunities reinforces this nexus. The transfer of skills between the two groups strengthens the nexus, with terrorist organizations outsourcing tasks like document forgery or money laundering to criminal networks. Prisons facilitate this transfer by allowing interaction between criminals and potential terrorists. Weak or failed states contribute significantly by providing a permissive environment for these groups to operate, sometimes even establishing de facto control over regions. In some cases, state actors themselves may be complicit, complicating countermeasures.

To counter the crime-terror nexus, the study recommends several strategies. Enhanced cooperation among agencies is crucial for effective counterterrorism and organized crime efforts. Intelligence, law enforcement, customs, and prison authorities must improve communication and data-sharing. Local authorities and communities should engage in preventing crime and terrorism, linking ordinary crimes to terrorism funding and fostering strong community relationships. Countering terrorism financing is vital, involving both large-scale and small-scale activities. Collaboration with the private banking sector can aid this effort. Research should explore the state's role, including how weak governance and state sponsorship contribute to the nexus. Expanding investigations to examine the criminal activities of terrorist groups can enhance counter-terrorism efforts, potentially requiring legislative changes and increased capacity to address terrorism-linked crimes.

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List of abbreviations

E.U.	European Union
ELN	National Liberation Army
Europol	European Union Agency for Law Enforcement Cooperation
FARC	Revolutionary Armed Forces of Colombia
FTF	Foreign terrorist fighters
ICSR	International Centre for the Study of Radicalisation
INCB	International Narcotics Control Board
IRA	Provisional Irish Republican Army
ISIS/L	Islamic State of Iraq and Syria/ and the Levant
KfR	Kidnapping for Ransom
OC	Organised crime
PMF	Popular Mobilization Forces
TCO	Transnational criminal organizations
TE-SAT	Terrorism Situation and Trend Report
UNODC	United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime

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Introduction

In recent years, the intersection of terrorism and organized crime, often referred to as the crime-terror nexus, has become a significant global issue. This study explores the complex dynamics of this nexus, examining how these distinct phenomena interact, collaborate, and learn from each other. While terrorist groups primarily pursue political objectives through violence, organized crime is typically driven by financial motives (Omeliicheva & Markowitz, 2021; Makarenko, 2004). Despite their differing goals, both entities frequently employ similar tactics and exploit overlapping environments, blurring the lines between them. This research aims to uncover the factors underlying this convergence.

Traditionally, terrorism and organized crime were viewed as separate entities with distinct motivations and methods (Omeliicheva & Markowitz, 2021). However, emerging evidence suggests an increasing union and opportunistic alliances between the two. This convergence threatens global security by providing terrorist organizations with new funding and expertise, while enabling criminal enterprises to further their political objectives (Makarenko, 2004). Several key factors drive this phenomenon. Globalization has created a more interconnected international landscape, allowing the free movement of weapons, capital, and personnel across borders. This connectivity offers terrorist and criminal organizations new opportunities for resource acquisition and collaboration (Omeliicheva & Markowitz, 2021; Makarenko, 2004). Additionally, the rise of weak or failed states has fostered environments where these groups can operate with impunity (Omeliicheva & Markowitz, 2021; Wang, 2010).

This research aims to analyse the complex challenges posed by the crime-terror nexus and propose potential solutions to address this issue. The study investigates three main factors of convergence: the financing of terrorism through illicit activities, the transfer of skills between organized crime and terrorist groups, and the role of weak state in facilitating their operations. The primary research question of this study is: "What are the factors contributing to the crime-terror nexus?" This question is further divided into three subsidiary questions, each addressing one of the above-mentioned factors, to provide a comprehensive analysis of this complex phenomenon.

The research is organized into four chapters. The first chapter presents the problem statement, detailing the research subject, objectives, and questions. It also highlights the relevance of the research and situates the research questions within their context, providing a conceptual framework. The second chapter outlines the methodology, describing the research methods, data collection techniques, sampling procedures, and data analysis.

The third chapter offers a broad literature review, examining both academic and governmental sources. This review explains key concepts such as terrorism, organized crime, and the crime-terror nexus, and explores the three factors of convergence: financing terrorism, skills transfer, and the role of weak

states. The fourth chapter of the literature review presents specific case studies, followed by recommendations based on the findings. Throughout the literature review, insights from expert respondents are integrated. The thesis concludes with a conclusion that addresses the research questions.

1 Problem statement

1.1 Research subject and objectives

The subject of the master thesis is the nexus between terrorism and organised crime. The research delves into the dynamics of the crime-terror nexus, examining how organised crime and terrorist groups, once viewed as fundamentally distinct, have increasingly intertwined their motivations, organisations and operations progressing towards deeper levels of collaboration and even convergence (Kulic and Bolhuis, 2023; Makarenko, 2004). Research has shown that criminal organisations and terrorist groups appear to learn from each other, adopting each other's tactics and strategies and frequently partner with one another (Wang, 2010). They use each other's expertise, skills, networks, and institutional structures for mutual advantage (Europol, 2023; Omelicheva and Markowitz, 2021). Among the shifting geopolitics and the newfound of transnational reach, non-state violent actors have adapted their criminal *modus operandi* to further their aims (Basra and Neumann, 2016). As a result, terrorist organisations have increasingly focused on criminal activities such as drug trafficking and smuggling to raise funds for their operations and criminal groups have engaged in political activities to manipulate operational conditions present in the weak states (Makarenko, 2004; Omelicheva and Markowitz, 2021; Wang 2010). The two actors share both organizational and operational characteristics and tend to adopt similar methods, yet they are striving different ends (Wang, 2010). The main purpose of the relation between the groups is to accomplish the groups' goals (Omelicheva and Markowitz, 2021).

The emergence of the crime-terror nexus can be explained on the basis of two dominant paradigms; the enabling role of globalization and the permissive role of “ungoverned” and “poorly governed” states (Omelicheva and Markowitz, 2021). It has been argued that globalization has facilitated the convergence of criminal organisations and terrorist organisations (Sullivan and Bunker, 2013). Catherine de Bolle, Executive Director of Europol, states that organized crime (OC) is a structural threat characterized by evolving methods and technology use, with enabling crimes becoming more visible and violent and infiltrating legal economies more deeply (De Bolle, 2024). According to Makarenko (2004), there is a growing reliance on cross-border criminal activities facilitated by “open borders, weak states, immigration flows, financial technology, accessible global transportation infrastructure and a common interest in establishing political control in order to secure future operations.”

Globalization has significantly facilitated the **financing of terrorism** (Omelicheva and Markowitz, 2021). According to the National Security Council of the White House (2018), the expansion of global trade and financial networks has enabled transnational criminal organizations (TCOs) and terrorist groups to more easily collaborate and share resources. As financial markets have become globalized, so have opportunities for illicit groups to transact with each other. This has allowed terrorist

organizations to tap into the lucrative global drug trade to finance their activities (Hernández, 2013). For example, the terrorist group Hezbollah has forged ties with drug trafficking organizations like the Zetas in Mexico, allowing it to leverage the drug trade to generate funding (Hernández, 2013). According to the International Narcotics Control Board (INCB), the Taliban in Afghanistan have profited extensively from the country's opium production, earning an estimated \$3 billion annually from the heroin trade (INCB, 2021).

Globalization has also enabled the **transfer of skills** and tactics between criminal and terrorist groups. Terrorist organizations have adopted the techniques of criminal groups, such as the "propaganda of the deed" used for strategic communication and intimidation. This technique refers to the use of direct, often violent actions to inspire broader social or political change (Miklaucic and Brewer, 2013). Equally, many transnational criminal organizations have incorporated terrorist violence into their operations (Miklaucic and Brewer, 2013). Additionally, the rise of new financial technologies like mobile payments and digital currencies has magnified the threat from illicit financial flows, making it easier for terrorist and criminal groups to move and launder money globally (INCB, 2021). This has further empowered the crime-terror nexus. All of these factors have enabled terrorists and criminals to exploit the dark side of globalization and forge mutually beneficial relationships (Europol, 2023; Omelicheva and Markowitz, 2021).

In addition, **weak states** and "ungoverned" territories have created a permissive environment for the interfusion of criminal and terrorist actors. Creating a "safe haven" for the emergence of the crime-terror nexus and where terrorist and criminal groups can operate with impunity (Omelicheva and Markowitz, 2021). Regions with limited state capacity, porous borders, and high levels of corruption have become hubs for the convergence of these illicit networks (Omelicheva and Markowitz, 2021; Phillips and Schiele, 2023). Examples of these territories are found in conflict and post-conflict areas such as in Africa, the Middle East and Asia (Omelicheva and Markowitz, 2021). In the same time, the emergence of the crime-terror nexus makes a state vulnerable and weak (Omelicheva and Markowitz, 2021). States play a prominent role in the existence of the crime-terror nexus.

1.2 Research questions

The nexus between organised crime and terrorism is increasingly complex and sophisticated, which is directly challenging the security of the states at national and international level (Wang, 2010). Despite the increasing international law enforcement pressure, the nexus between criminals and terrorists has evolved during the past several decades alarming governments around the globe (Makarenko, 2004; Phillips and Schiele, 2023). As mentioned by Van der Wilt and Paulissen (2019), the former Dutch Minister of Foreign Affairs, Bert Koenders stated that *"the more we succeed in taking back territory from ISIS, cutting off its funds from the sale of oil and preventing weapons from reaching them, the more they will seek cooperation with criminal networks. ISIS is now embracing the criminals they*

once despised, because they can deliver the weapons, money, drugs and personnel that ISIS needs. This is a toxic partnership that we need to detect early and stop in its tracks”.

Despite these developments, the outcomes of the criminal-terrorist nexus remain relatively underexplored within scholarly discourse (Europol, 2023; Omelicheva and Markowitz, 2021). Yet, the collaboration between criminal organisations and terrorist organisations challenges the security of the state and the region (Makarenko, 2004; Wang, 2010). The worldwide anti-terror campaign and the extremely repressing approach against the funding of terrorism make cooperation between criminal organisations and terrorists a rational choice for both (Wang, 2010). As reported in Europol’s report “Terrorism situation and trends report 2023”, the links between terrorists and organised crime remains unstructured and opportunistic (Europol, 2023). The nature of the relation between groups varies and can include one-off, short-term and long-term relationships (Makarenko, 2004; Wang, 2010). The research aims to fill this gap by analysing factors contributing to this relation.

Through comprehensive analysis and empirical research, this study seeks to contribute to a deeper understanding of the dynamics between criminal organizations and terrorist organizations and provide the academic field with new perspectives. The main objective of this study is to provide a critical analysis of the factors that facilitate to the crime-terror nexus. The research focuses on: the financing of terrorism through criminal activities, the skills transfer between criminal organizations and terrorist groups, and the weak states where these groups operate.

The main research question for the study is:

- **What are the factors that contribute to the crime-terror nexus?**

This main research question is divided into three sub-questions:

- **How does the financing of terrorism through criminal activities contribute to the crime-terror nexus?**
- **How does the transfer of skills between groups contribute to the crime-terror nexus?**
- **How does the state play a role in contributing to the crime-terror nexus?**

1.3 Conceptual framework

Figure 1 Conceptual framework of the study on the crime-terror nexus

The conceptual framework presented in Figure 1 starts with the two paradigms that explain the emergence of the crime-terror nexus: the enabling role of globalization and the permissive role of weak states (Omelicheva and Markowitz, 2021). These two paradigms are further divided into factors contributing to the crime-terror nexus.

The first step is the conceptual definition. The concepts of the study are not externally observable and are inferred from other observable characteristics that are presented in the literature review (Bijleveld, 2015). **Globalization** is not an observable concept and is represented in this study by the financing of terrorism (Basra, Neumann and Brunner, 2016) and the skills transfer between the groups (Basra, Neumann and Brunner, 2016; Phillips and Schiele, 2023). This shows how globalization facilitates the movement of people, goods, money, and information across borders (Makarenko, 2004). **Weak states** are defined by the black hole state (Makarenko, 2004) and the state as the cause of the crime-terror nexus (Kulic and Bolhuis, 2023). The second step is the operational definition. Operationalization concerns the way in which the concepts are measured (Bijleveld, 2015, p. 38-40). For this study a critical literature review will be conducted (Jesson, Matheson and Lacey, 2011). The concepts are measured through a critical analysis of the literature review. The literature delves further on the factors contributing to the convergence of organized crime and terrorism:

- The concept of **financing of terrorism** is studied through criminal activities. Criminal organizations can provide terrorists with the funds they need to carry out attacks. This can be done through criminal activities such as drug trafficking, but also a terrorist organization can be part of the drug trade to raise funds for their activities (INCB, 2021; Makarenko, 2004; Omelicheva and Markowitz, 2021).

- The concept of **skills transfer** is observable through the skills that are exchanged between organized groups and terrorist organizations. The literature delves into three questions: what skills are transferred (skills for operational support), how and by whom the skills are carried out (through recruitment), and where the transfer happens (in prisons).
- The concept of **weak states** is analysed in the literature by the black hole syndrome (Makarenko, 2004) and the state as a cause to the crime-terror nexus (Kulic and Bolhuis, 2023; Omelicheva and Markowitz, 2021) which provide a safe haven for criminal and terrorist organizations to operate.

2 Methodological approach

2.1 Research method

The chosen research method is a qualitative, mixed-methods approach, specifically including a critical literature review and a limited number of expert interviews. This qualitative approach is well-suited to the study as it provides a comprehensive understanding of the intricate relationship between terrorism and organized crime, allowing for an in-depth exploration of existing literature and empirical studies (Bijleveld, 2015). A literature review is not merely a summary of previous research but a research method in itself. It is essential for identifying research gaps, developing theoretical frameworks, and situating one's work within the existing body of knowledge (Paré and Kitsiou, 2017; Sheppard, 2019). In this study, the literature review is conducted with the dual purpose of identifying research gaps and formulating a theoretical framework (Paré and Kitsiou, 2017; Sheppard, 2019).

The choice of a literature review is justified by the nature of the research topic. The crime-terror nexus is a complex and multifaceted phenomenon that requires a nuanced understanding beyond mere quantitative analysis. According to Europol's "Terrorism Situation and Trends Report 2023," the links between terrorists and organized crime remain unstructured and opportunistic (Europol, 2023). By delving into existing literature, this study aims to uncover the underlying dynamics that shape the intersection between terrorism and organized crime (Bijleveld, 2015).

The literature review process involves systematically searching, evaluating, and synthesizing the existing body of work on a particular topic (Paré and Kitsiou, 2017). A critical literature review involves a systematic and comprehensive examination of academic articles, books, policy briefs, and think-tank reports pertinent to the crime-terror nexus. The literature review process is often iterative, with revisiting earlier steps as needed (Paré and Kitsiou, 2017). This review process is guided by a critical lens, involving not only summarizing existing literature but also analysing and evaluating the arguments, methodologies, and findings presented in the selected sources. Different theories are critically examined to provide a deeper understanding of the subject (Jesson, Matheson, and Lacey, 2011).

2.2 Data collection and analysis method

2.2.1 Systematic literature review

The chosen data collection method is a systematic literature review, executed through a step-by-step plan. First, the research question and objectives are formulated, clearly defining the scope and focus of the study (Paré and Kitsiou, 2017). Specifically, the research aims to explore various aspects of the crime-terror nexus, including the financing of terrorism, skills transfer between groups, and their operational regions.

Next, relevant academic literature is systematically searched using databases, search engines, and other sources to find peer-reviewed articles (Paré and Kitsiou, 2017). For example, using Google Scholar. Three main criteria are considered when selecting articles: the relevance, the date of publication, and the peer-review status. **Despite the age of Tamara Makarenko's articles on the crime-terror continuum of 2004, her work is included due to her prominence in this field.** Also, input from the seminar 'Taking Stock of Global Security Trends,' organized by Egmont – the Royal Institute for International Relations and the Belgian Ministry of the Interior in Brussels on March 8, 2024, is used for the problem statement, defining the relevance of the study, and providing recommendations.

The content of the literature is then screened based on pre-determined criteria, selecting both academic and governmental sources, such as from the United Nations and various ministries of defence and foreign affairs of different countries. The pre-determined criteria included the history of the nexus, definitions of organized crime and terrorism, and factors contributing to the crime-terror nexus. These form the structure of the literature review of the master thesis. To assess the quality and validity of the articles, the methodology, findings, and conclusions of the articles are critically evaluated.

Data analysis in this qualitative research involves synthesizing and interpreting the findings from the selected articles. Key data from the included studies are extracted and organized, identifying patterns, themes, gaps, and contradictions (Paré and Kitsiou, 2017; Sheppard, 2019) When a certain pattern appeared in multiple articles, such as the emergence of the crime-terror nexus during the Cold War, it was assigned the code "cold war" for further analysis. Another examples, is looking into the definitions of the crime-terror nexus and finding regularly the contradiction with narco-terrorism, which would then get the code “narco-terrorism” for further analysis. This coding process was applied to all recurring information, resulting in a comprehensive coding scheme presented in the attachments list on page 43.

Finally, the findings are analysed and synthesized in a meaningful way to draw new insights to form the collective body of the study (Paré and Kitsiou, 2017). This resulted in a comprehensive and structured literature review of the crime-terror nexus presented in the master thesis.

2.2.2 Expert interviews

Due to the complexity of the topic concerning the convergence of organized crime and terrorist organizations, four expert interviews were conducted to corroborate findings from the literature and provide additional insights. A purposive sampling method was used, where experts with experience in counter-terrorism and/or organized crime studies were contacted via the social media platform LinkedIn (Decorte and Zaitch, 2017). Out of ten contacted experts, four responded and agreed to be interviewed. The interviews were conducted in August 2024, either through video conferencing or, when possible, in person. Some respondents were reluctant to participate due to the sensitive nature of

the topic. Therefore, the interviews were not recorded; only notes were taken during the conversations. To protect the respondents from any potential repercussions, they were anonymized throughout the study. Each respondent was assigned a code (R1, R2, R3, and R4) based on their expertise: R1 and R2 are UN staff working on counter-terrorism, and R3 and R4 are researchers specializing in transnational organized crime and/or counter-terrorism sanctions.

The interviews were semi-structured, guided by an interview guide, which can be found on page 44 (Baarda and Loonstra, 2020). The first step of the interview process was the introduction. In this introduction, the researcher provided the respondents with information about the topic and objectives of the research, along with the expected duration of the interview. The respondents were also informed that the data would be handled confidentially and that their anonymity would be guaranteed (Baarda and Loonstra, 2020). The interview guide covered various topics, including the definition of key concepts (terrorism, organized crime, narco-terrorism, and the crime-terror nexus). The respondents were then asked detailed questions about the factors contributing to the nexus; the financing of terrorism, the transfer of skills, and the role of weak states. Finally, respondents were asked to provide recommendations for addressing the issue of the crime-terror nexus. The data obtained from the expert interviews were coded manually, using a predefined coding scheme, without the use of software.

3 Literature review framework

The literature delves into the factors contributing to the crime-terror nexus. The first part gives a brief history of the crime-terror nexus. In the second part the various concepts are broadly defined. The third part of the literature delves into the factors contributing to the nexus. The literature review concludes with case studies and recommendations. Throughout the literature review, insights from expert respondents are integrated.

3.1 History

The concept of a crime-terrorism nexus is not new. This convergence has evolved over time and has been influenced by various geopolitical, economic, and social factors. The crime-terror nexus can be traced back to the **Cold War era**, where ideological lines often blurred, leading to opportunistic alliances. For instance, during the 1970s and 1980s, various guerrilla groups in Latin America, such as the Colombian FARC (Revolutionary Armed Forces of Colombia), engaged in narco-trafficking to fund their insurgencies. This period marked the beginning of criminal organizations and terrorist groups exploiting similar illicit markets (Basra and Neumann, 2016; Makarenko, 2004).

In the early 1990s, following the **collapse of the Soviet Union**, terrorist involvement in organized crime to fund future operations emerged as a significant concern (Basra and Neumann, 2016; Makarenko, 2004; Wang, 2010). Due to their secretive nature, terrorist groups often find it difficult to legally obtain resources and have limited access to conventional markets. This issue became more pronounced after the Cold War, as state sponsorship declined, compelling these groups to seek alternative sources of support (Phillips and Schiele, 2023). Organised criminal activities have then become a major revenue source for terrorist groups worldwide (Makarenko, 2004). As a result, collaboration between criminals and terrorists has become a significant factor in funding and meeting the operational needs of terrorist organizations. Such cooperation offers numerous advantages, including access to specialized knowledge (e.g., smuggling), specialized services (e.g., forged identity documents), operational support (e.g., human trafficking), and financial support (e.g., involvement in the trade of illicit goods). It is believed that the crime-terror nexus is a product of changes in the post-Cold War environment (Omelicheva and Markowitz, 2021; Wang, 2010).

As Makarenko (2004, p. 129) states, *“The 1990s can be described as the decade in which the crime-terror nexus was consolidated: the rise of transnational organised crime and the changing nature of terrorism mean that two traditionally separate phenomena have begun to reveal many operational and organizational similarities”*.

The terrorist attacks on **September 11, 2001**, and the ensuing **Global War on Terror** highlighted the nexus between crime and terror. Al-Qaeda's financing mechanisms included money laundering, drug trafficking, and counterfeit goods. Similarly, the Taliban in Afghanistan have long been associated

with the opium trade, which funds their insurgency against the Afghan government and international forces. Following the 9/11 terrorist attacks, the United States has played an important role in the war against terror. It has adopted a broad and stringent approach to combat the financing of terrorism, freezing assets and blocking financial transactions from charities and organizations associated with terrorists (Wang, 2010). Global efforts targeting terrorist funding have made cooperation between terrorist groups risky. The intensified counter-terror policies and measures against financing have constrained financial flows within and between terrorist groups. Consequently, terrorist groups seek alternative funding sources. This pressure has potentially driven more alliances between terrorist groups and organized crime. Research suggests that crackdowns on funding sources have forced terrorists to increasingly turn to criminal activities like kidnapping for fundraising (Phillips and Schiele, 2023).

3.2 Definitions

3.2.1 Understanding terrorism, organised crime and narco-terrorism

A variety of definitions can be found for **terrorism** in the literature. However, there is still no comprehensive convention on the concept of terrorism, only sectorial conventions that address particular manifestations of political violence (Van der Wilt and Paulussen, 2019). Therefore, terrorism has been a conceptual minefield, with ongoing debates about the attributes of politically motivated violence in academic and policy worlds (Omelicheva and Markowitz, 2021). Most of terrorist attacks committed globally are domestic in nature and perpetrated by insurgents fighting in civil wars (Omelicheva and Markowitz, 2021).

A common and widely accepted definition for terrorism is “*the deliberate threat or use of violence by non-state actors to achieve a political or social objective by intimidating a broader audience beyond the direct victims*” (Phillips and Schiele, 2023). The key components of this definition include (1) the use of violence, (2) the pursuit of political or social goals, and (3) the aim to intimidate a wider audience. The second component, in particular, is crucial for differentiating this form of violence from less-politically motivated violence (Phillips and Schiele, 2023). According to the United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime (UNODC) terrorism “*can be broadly understood as a method of coercion that utilizes or threatens to utilize violence in order to spread fear and thereby attain political or ideological goals*” (UNODC, 2018). Terrorist groups are essentially political entities driven by goals such as imposing their ideology or religion on a government or securing political rights for a particular group (Phillips and Schiele, 2023).

Organized crime groups are often networks of loosely affiliated individuals rather than strictly hierarchical organizations, partly in response to law enforcement pressure. The crimes committed by such groups can range from money laundering, human trafficking, drug smuggling and counterfeiting

of goods. Consequently, an organized crime group is defined as a group of individuals dedicated to committing serious crimes to gain profit or material benefit (Phillips and Schiele, 2023). Many organized crime groups differ significantly from the popular image of highly structured organizations like the Mafia. Since 2000, the United Nations Convention against Transnational Organized Crime has established a globally accepted definition of an organized criminal group: *"a group of three or more individuals existing for some time, working together to commit crimes for financial or material gain."* This definition was also incorporated into the EU's Council Framework Decision 2008/841/JHA on the fight against organized crime, dated on 24 October 2008, and remains a cornerstone in law enforcement's understanding of organized crime globally. Nevertheless, it falls short in capturing the complex and adaptable nature of contemporary organized crime networks (Europol, 2017). While the distinction between terrorist and criminal groups can sometimes be unclear, they are typically classified based on their primary motivations and actions (Phillips and Schiele, 2023). The United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime's definition for organised crime is the following: *"a continuing criminal enterprise that rationally works to profit from illicit activities that are often in great public demand. Its continuing existence is maintained through corruption of public officials and the use of intimidation, threats or force to protect its operations"* (UNODC, 2018).

The nexus has often been confused with **narco-terrorism** because the drug trade is a major source of profits for both terrorists and transnational organized crime (TOC) (Wang, 2010). The emergence of new terms like criminal insurgency driven by evolving gang and cartel activities and increasing criminal violence, particularly in Central America, has further complicated the understanding of the relationship between organized criminal actors and organized violence like terrorist organizations (Omelicheva and Markowitz, 2021).

In the literature, several examples of narco-terrorism can be found, especially in the 1980s and 1990s in Latin America during the rise of the Colombian drug cartels and figures like Pablo Escobar. Scholars debated whether narco-terrorism represented a true blurring of lines between criminals and terrorists (Basra and Neumann, 2016). For instance, Colombian authorities reported that the Medellin cocaine cartel hired the ELN (National Liberation Army) to plant car bombs in 1993 because they lacked the capability to conduct terrorist acts themselves. Despite using terror tactics such as bombings and assassinations, the primary motivation of the cartel remained illicit profit maximization (Makarenko, 2004). According to US government officials, the FARC (Revolutionary Armed Forces of Colombia) allegedly formed alliances with Mexican drug-trafficking groups to obtain weapons, exchanging cocaine for arms shipments (Makarenko, 2004). The FARC has consistently denied these claims. Additionally, groups like the Taliban have relied on Afghanistan's heroin production, Hezbollah has invested in South America's illicit narcotics industry since the 1980s, and organizations like the Irish Republican Army (IRA) have engaged in activities such as smuggling petrol, cigarettes, and counterfeiting consumer goods (Basra, Neumann, and Brunner, 2016). Building on the history of

narco-terrorism, the use of crime became an important factor in the evolution of terrorism (Makarenko, 2004).

3.2.2 The concept “crime-terror nexus”

Even though the nexus between terrorism and (transnational) organised crime (TOC) has been discussed at least since the 1980s, it is especially in the last few years that there has been an increased interest in the topic by scholars and international/regional organisations (Makarenko, 2004; Van der Wilt and Paulussen, 2019). At the start of the 21st century a growing number of groups have showed characteristics of organised crime and terrorism. **They have incorporated economic and political objectives into their remit and lost sight of their original motivations and aims, making it analytically difficult to make a distinction between the two organizations** (Makarenko, 2004). This further makes it difficult to find a clear definition of the crime-terror nexus and many definitions can be found through the years.

In 2014, the **UN Security Council** first referred to the phenomenon of foreign terrorist fighters (FTF) and expressed in its Resolution 2195 its concern *'that terrorists benefit from transnational organised crime in some regions, including from the trafficking of arms, persons, drugs, and artefacts and from the illicit trade in natural resources, including gold and other precious metals and stones, minerals, wildlife, charcoal and oil, as well as from kidnapping for ransom and other crimes including extortion and bank robbery'* (Van der Wilt and Paulussen, 2019, p. 316). In 2019, the UN Security Council unanimously adopted Resolution 2482, expressing its concern about connections between terrorism and organized crime, noting the benefits for terrorists in particular (Phillips and Schiele, 2023). Also, in its Resolution the UN General Assembly, by which—the UN Convention against Transnational Organised Crime was adopted noted *“with deep concern the growing links between transnational organised crime and terrorist crimes”* and called upon all states *“to recognize the links between transnational organised criminal activities and acts of terrorism”* (Van der Wilt and Paulussen, 2019).

In 2016, the **International Centre for the Study of Radicalisation (ICSR)**, in its report titled *“Criminal Pasts, Terrorist Futures: European Jihadists and the New Crime–Terror Nexus”*, looked at the profile of 79% of the European jihadists and concluded: *“With Islamic State and the ongoing mobilisation of European jihadists, the phenomenon, that is, the presence of former criminals in terrorist group, has become more pronounced, more visible, and more relevant. In many European countries, the majority of jihadist foreign fighters are former criminals”* (Van der Wilt and Paulussen, 2019).

One year later, in 2017, Dick Schoof, the former **Dutch National Coordinator for Security and Counterterrorism** stated that *“the connections between jihadists and criminals are getting stronger and is thus worrying the Dutch intelligence and prosecution services, because it will be easier for*

terrorists to obtain weapons” (Van der Wilt and Paulussen, 2019). In that same year, the previous Dutch Minister of Foreign Affairs, Bert Koenders, gave a speech to the plenary meeting of the Foreign Terrorist Fighters Working Group of the Global Counterterrorism Forum and mentioned that the “*nexus is growing*”, that it is “*an alarming development*” and that it constitutes “*an area we’ll need to focus on more in the coming period.*”

Despite these developments, the concept of crime-terror nexus has not only failed to gain significant interest among scholars, but many have dismissed it as being overly broad. Key criticisms include the assumptions that terrorist or criminal organisations function as unified, hierarchical structures, and that ideological and criminal motives are entirely separate (Basra and Neumann, 2016). According to R1, terrorist organizations seek visibility, while criminal organizations operate clandestinely. **However, all four respondents agree that both terrorist and criminal organizations aim to gain control over territory. The respondents emphasize that the primary objective of these groups is to gain territory, as it is closely linked to power. They agree that both groups are embedded in specific territories, which they seek to dominate. R1 notes that since both groups desire control over the same territory, they tend to compete with each other rather than collaborate. However, R2 argues that because they share the same territory, they have common ground and tend to work together. This difference in perspectives highlights the lack of a unified view on the crime-terror nexus.**

The conceptual distinctions between terrorism and organised crime are likewise fuzzy (Van der Wilt and Paulussen, 2019). The consequences of this lack of conceptualization and clear definitions create not only confusion but also opportunities for the nexus between terrorism and organised crimes. The lack of conceptual precision in terrorism and organised crime hinders law enforcement's reliance on the legality principle, which stipulated the existence of an accessible and foreseeable criminal provision before the commission of that offence (Van der Wilt and Paulussen, 2019). Confusion about the proper limits of the concepts, especially in the case of blurring borders, may also question whether suspects are actually guilty of a criminal offence (Van der Wilt and Paulussen, 2019).

3.2.2.1 The profit-ideology dichotomy

For a long time, organised crime and terrorism were seen as two distinct phenomena, separated by the profit-ideology dichotomy. The two categories are often distinguished on the basis of motivation (Omelicheva and Markowitz, 2021). In the literature it is noted that terrorists differ from criminals in their motivations; terrorists see themselves as altruists working towards a greater good, whereas criminals are driven by the desire to increase personal wealth without serving any cause (Phillips and Schiele, 2023). Crime is seen as a profit-maximizing, non-politically and non-ideologically motivated phenomenon, and terrorism as strictly ideologically motivated phenomenon, without any profit driven actions (Kulic and Bolhuis, 2023; Wang, 2010). The dichotomy emphasizes how a terrorist organization is different from criminal organisations, as it pursues political rather than economic goals

(Phillips and Schiele, 2023; Wang, 2010). However, the lines that separate organised crime from terrorism are increasingly blurred (Kulic and Bolhuis, 2023). The application of the profit-ideology dichotomy has been fraught with challenges (Omelicheva and Markowitz, 2021). **The rigid dichotomy has been criticized because it overlooks the flexibility of the crime-terror nexus, where crime can serve as a mobilizer for terrorists, ensuring not only funding, but also effective recruitment, governance, and operational capabilities** (Kulic and Bolhuis, 2023). These challenges will be discussed later in the literature.

3.2.2.2 The crime-terror continuum

Another approach to the crime-terror nexus is the crime-terror continuum by Tamara Makarenko (2004). The crime-terror continuum seeks to highlight the importance of overlapping counter-terrorist and anti-crime policies as a way of formulating an effective state response to evolving converging threats (Makarenko, 2004). Out of the four respondents, three heard of the crime-terror continuum by Makarenko. According to R4 the continuum is a useful way to approach the nexus, as it acknowledges the fluidity of a group depending on different variables and the range of relationships between terrorist groups and criminal groups. The three respondents agree that the most well-known example of convergence is the IRA and the FARC. However, R1 believes it is rare that there is a continuity. According to the respondent a convergence rarely happens, most of the time it is mainly terrorist organizations engaging directly in criminal activities.

The crime-terror continuum, as conceptualized by Tamara Makarenko, is a theoretical framework that describes the dynamic and evolving relationship between organised crime and terrorism. **It posits that these two phenomena are not mutually exclusive but rather exist on a spectrum, with groups capable of sliding between criminal and terrorist activities depending on their environment and goals.** The continuum illustrates how “*a single group can slide up and down the scale, between the traditionally called organised crime and terrorism, depending on the environment in which it operates*” (Kulic and Bolhuis, 2023; Makarenko, 2004).

Figure 2 The crime-terror continuum. Source: Makarenko (2004).

According to Makarenko the criminal organisations and terrorist organisations share the same space of operation and therefore there is a risk that they reach a central point of convergence at the centre of the continuum. At this point the ideology-profit dichotomy is no longer visible. The criminal and terrorist organisations converge into a single entity that shows characteristics of both groups. It has the potential to transform itself into an entity positioned at the opposite end of the continuum from which it began (Kulic and Bolhuis, 2023). Transformation occurs to such a degree that the ultimate aims and motivations of the organization have changed (Makarenko, 2004). It becomes a powerful and destructive organization seeking both political and financial ambition (Makarenko, 2004).

Tactical and strategic alliances

Before getting to the point of transformation and convergence, the criminal organisations and terrorist organisations typically engage in various activities that set the stage for their eventual collaboration. For example, terrorist groups that commit criminal activities for operations purposes or criminal organisations that use terror tactics for operations purposes (Makarenko, 2004). The linkages between organised criminal groups and terrorists have occurred in a combination of ways, both **tactical** and **strategic**. A **tactical relationship** means a one-spot or short timeframe cooperation without any complementary enduring goals. An example of a one-spot cooperation, is the alliance between the Italian Red Bridges (a terrorist organization) with Naples Camorra (a criminal organization) in the early 1980s. The terrorist activities of the Red Bridges had been seriously limited by the Italian authorities. Therefore, they wanted to establish this alliance with the Naples Camorra to exchange services and to combat their common enemy, the Italian authorities (Makarenko, 2012; Wang, 2010). A **strategic alliance** between organised crime groups and terrorists is based on their consistent interests and aim to achieve mutual expectations of long-term goals (Wang, 2010). For example, the Moscow-based Chechen Mafia and the Grozny-based Chechen guerrillas are two distinct groups that formed an enduring cooperation. The Chechen Mafia, involved in organized crime in Moscow, and the Chechen guerrillas, who engaged in assassinations, kidnappings, and terrorism against the Russian government, initially had different aims and ideologies. The Russian government's military response to the guerrillas' actions resulted in the destruction of Chechen cities and the suppression of both the guerrillas and the mafia. This severe crackdown forced the Chechen Mafia to cooperate with the Chechen guerrillas. The Chechen Mafia began to financially support the guerrillas. In exchange, the guerrillas provided protection services, intelligence, and weapons to the Mafia (Wang, 2010).

Convergence

The **convergence** can take place in two modes. On the one hand we have the criminal groups that display political motivations. Those groups use terror tactics to gain political leverage and to block anti-crime legislation that jeopardizes their criminal activities with the objective to secure their operations (Kulic and Bolhuis, 2023). For example, the Italian mafia engaged in terrorism as a tactical

tool to force the government into negotiation and compromise (Makarenko, 2004). In Central America, the criminals have the capacity to evolve into “criminal soldiers” of street gangs. They operate like insurgents (rebels fighting against the state) but with criminal goals (profit, power, etc.) instead of political ones (Omeliicheva and Markowitz, 2021). **By simultaneously focusing on criminal and political goals, these groups are able to use two sets of networks which allow them to shift focus from the application of terrorism to the application of other crimes and/or to pursue multiple objectives simultaneously** (Makarenko, 2004).

On the other hand, we have terrorist groups that were initially ideology driven, change into criminal enterprises using political rhetoric as a façade for perpetrating criminal activities. By combatting the financing of terrorism, some terrorist groups have transformed to organisations with a “profit-minded agencies” (Wang, 2010). This transformation renders them a different entity, solely pursuing profit through illegal activities masked by their dwindling political agenda (Kulic and Bolhuis, 2023; Makarenko, 2004; Omeliicheva and Markowitz, 2021). The systematic involvement of a terrorist group in criminal activities shifts the terrorists’ ideological agendas to profit-seeking motivations and vice versa among organised criminal actors (Omeliicheva and Markowitz, 2021). **The convergence of economic and ideological goals of one entity, creates a hybrid criminal-political entity (Kulic and Bolhuis, 2023). The convergence is mostly conceptual and is the most difficult type of nexus to identify (Kulic and Bolhuis, 2023).**

3.3 The factors on the crime-terror nexus

3.3.1 Financing terrorism

The International Monetary Fund (2023), defines terrorism financing as the raising and processing of funds to supply terrorists with resources. After the collapse of the Soviet Union and the decline of state sponsorship, terrorist groups needed to seek alternative sources of funding their organizations and activities. The funding of terrorism can be separated into two categories: the funding of the organizations itself and the funding of the attacks. **If we look into the funding of the organizations, running a terrorist organization can be costly. Hierarchically structured groups like the IRA or ETA had million-dollar budgets, covering a broad range of activities including weapons, military operations, training camps, salaries, and benefits for the families of deceased or imprisoned fighters (Basra, Neumann, and Brunner, 2016). Furthermore, when terrorist groups evolve into insurgent armies or quasi-states, such as Islamic State in Syria and Iraq, al-Shabaab in Somalia, or Hezbollah in Lebanon, they become de facto governments, funding everything from schools to infrastructure necessitating considerable funding to ensure the continuation of these activities (Basra et al., 2016).**

The attacks conducted in the West operates largely independently from the centralized budgets of groups like al-Qaeda and Islamic State (Basra et al., 2016). Terrorist jihadist groups have encouraged

their Western supporters to self-finance and to carry out low-cost, easy-to-execute attacks (Basra et al., 2016). Islamic State has also encouraged loose networks, cell structures, and 'low-cost' attacks among their supporters abroad, while allocating substantial resources to manage their 'state' in Syria and Iraq (Basra et al., 2016). This strategy has been effective because jihadist activities in Europe aren't expensive. For example, becoming a foreign fighter typically requires little more than purchasing a plane ticket to Turkey. An AK-47 can be bought for less than €2,000, and a pistol costs even less. The expenses for buying a knife or renting a vehicle are minimal. The French Finance Minister mentioned that even the November 2015 Paris attacks were funded with an amount not exceeding €30,000. **Such amounts generally do not require external funding or a dedicated terrorist fundraising operation; they can be sourced from personal assets and savings, legitimate means such as work or loans, or small-scale criminal activities that terrorists with criminal backgrounds are accustomed to** (Basra et al., 2016).

This phenomenon can be understood through **three interconnected points** (Basra et al., 2016). Firstly, the vast majority of terrorist attacks in Europe do not require large sums of money or dependence on the financial resources of the terrorist organization. Islamic State and other jihadist groups deliberately strive to maintain low financial barriers to encourage broad participation among their supporters, regardless of their economic status. Secondly, jihadists have encouraged the use of 'ordinary' criminality to raise funds. Lastly, a combination of both findings, shows that they continue to do what they are familiar with and therefore terrorist funding by criminal means is likely to become more important (Basra and Neumann, 2016). As a result, it can be difficult to separate funds that were raised for terrorism, from money that is spent on other purposes (Basra and Neumann, 2016). The difficulty in detecting crime as a method of financing terrorism lies in the fact that it does not involve a change of behaviour, but merely a change of purpose. Individuals with criminal pasts often continue what they were doing in their earlier lives, except that the profits are used to finance terrorist attacks (Basra and Neumann, 2016).

It has been argued that criminal activities will increasingly serve as a crucial source of funding for terrorist operations, potentially becoming the primary financing method for terrorist groups (Basra et al., 2016 and Wang, 2010). Involvement in criminal activities has been a significant source of funding for terrorist organizations. According to the respondents it can be agreed that engaging in criminal activities is for terrorist organizations their only way of surviving. **As mentioned by R3 it's mainly about surviving and without money and funding a terrorist organization cannot survive.** In addition to loans, private donations, bank fraud, and business fraud, terrorist groups consistently emphasized the role of petty crime. As pointed out by R4,

Petty crime has been used for a long time in financing terrorism. These crimes include credit card fraud, insurance fraud, armed robbery, extortion of small businesses, selling counterfeit

documents, etc. Petty crimes have been used regardless of the size of the organization, but their prevalence in the overall fundraising seems to increase when law enforcement pressure mounts against the organization and it is no longer able to conduct serious crimes like trafficking or is unable to tax large swathes of the population.

Criminality plays thus a significant role in financing terrorist organisations (Basra and Neumann, 2016; Wang, 2010). Although terrorist groups have commonly been associated with trafficking in illicit narcotics, they have also engaged in a wide variety of other crimes such as fraud, trade in counterfeit products and human smuggling as source of profit (Makarenko, 2004; Wang, 2010).

Omeliicheva and Markowitz (2021) provide two explanations for this phenomenon. On the one hand, by consolidating the financial base of terrorist groups, organised criminal groups make terrorist organisations more durable and deadly (Omeliicheva and Markowitz, 2021). On the other hand, by acting alongside a terrorist organization that controls a territory, organized criminal groups can move freely without detection by the government (Omeliicheva and Markowitz, 2021). Cooperation with terrorists can provide significant advantages for organized criminals by destabilizing the political system, weakening law enforcement, and hindering international cooperation. Additionally, terrorist activities may divert law enforcement's attention away from organized crime, allowing criminals to operate with reduced scrutiny (Phillips and Schiele, 2023).

3.3.1.1 Drug trade

The most common criminal activity terrorist groups have been involved in is the illicit drug trade (Makarenko, 2004; Phillips and Schiele, 2023). Ine Van Wymersch, Belgian National Drugs Commissioner states that the drug market is very resilient. Despite the global changes, the drug market remains resilient, with increased violence and weapons use in Europe and more cross-border connections with non-state violent groups (Van Wymersch, 2024). Many terrorist groups engage in drug production or trafficking to fund their activities or for personal gain. For instance, the FARC in Colombia is heavily involved in the cocaine industry, not only by imposing taxes but also by actively trafficking the drug. Similarly, the PKK and the Taliban are known to traffic heroin and other drugs in their respective regions (Phillips and Schiele, 2023). Research shows that there is a connection between drug trafficking and terrorism (Makarenko, 2004).

On the contrary to labour-intensive illicit economies such as the cultivation of drug crops, the smuggling of drug is less labour intensive and needs fewer people (Omeliicheva and Markowitz, 2021). Using the money from drug trafficking gives terrorist groups greater mobility and flexibility. Diamonds, oil, copper and other minerals are known as “point-source” natural resources extracted from specific geographic area and make it easier form authorities to exercise control over that area and their extraction (Omeliicheva and Markowitz, 2021). In essence, diamonds and oil are more tractable,

compared to illicit drugs. The type of criminal activity defined by the mode of resource extraction, conditions the nature of the relationship between crime and terrorism. **This finding is also reflected in the respondents' answers. According to them, the criminal activities most commonly used by terrorist organizations for funding depend on their location.** Terrorist organizations adapt to their environment and the resources available to them. An example given by both R1 and R4 is ISIS selling archaeological sites on the dark market, because they had access to it.

R4 points out,

This largely depends on criminal opportunities available in the area where the group operates. If the area is a cross roads for illegal migration then human trafficking or smuggling of migrants will be prevalent. If the area attracts foreign engineers/businesses working in mining or the petroleum sector then KfR will be the preferred modus operandi for raising funds, and so on. So, a terrorist organization will get involved in the drug trade if its area of operations is already known for drug production/trafficking and the opportunity presents itself to the group.

According to Omelicheva and Markowitz (2021) understanding the nature of the resource structure matters for approaches to countering the crime–terror nexus. The convergence of criminal and terrorist networks, along with the self-financing of attacks, complicates the traditional understanding of terrorist financing. Instead of focusing on specific transactions and income sources linked to terrorism, it may be more effective to examine individuals, their backgrounds, and their financial histories (Basra et al., 2016; Omelicheva and Markowitz, 2021).

3.3.2 Skills transfer

3.3.2.1 Operational support (what?)

One of the most troubling aspects of the emerging crime-terror nexus is the potential transfer of criminal skills to terrorists (Basra et al., 2016). Collaboration with organized crime provides terrorist groups with significant operational support while minimizing risks compared to engaging in criminal activities independently or with other terrorist organizations (Phillips and Schiele, 2023). Terrorist groups benefit significantly from skills transferred from criminal networks, such as forging documents and accessing safe houses. These capabilities help terrorists evade authorities and enhance the chances of successful attacks (Basra et al., 2016). Respondents agree with this finding, noting that terrorist groups learn significantly from criminal organizations. **These organizations provide essential information, expertise, and skills, such as bomb-making techniques and ways to sell on the dark market. According to the respondents, it's primarily about efficiency, and terrorist groups heavily rely on criminal organizations.** Instead of developing these skills internally, terrorist networks often outsource them to criminal experts, as seen in the Paris attacks of November 2015, where former

criminals with ties to organized crime were recruited for their expertise in obtaining fake IDs (Basra et al., 2016).

Terrorist groups with lack of internal skills, compensate this lack by collaborating with organized crime (Basra et al., 2016). Outsourcing non-core tasks such as money laundering and extortion reduces the risk of exposure for terrorist groups, who lack expertise in these areas (Phillips and Schiele, 2023). For instance, terrorist groups avoid in-house narcotics trafficking because of the organized crime's control over this illicit market. Instead, they prefer to collaborate with criminal experts to meet their needs safely (Phillips and Schiele, 2023).

The value of individuals with criminal backgrounds for terrorist groups lies in how the merging of criminal and terrorist environments enhances these groups' ability to execute more frequent and deadly attacks. Criminals often possess useful skills such as dealing with law enforcement and understanding the limits of police powers. They are innovative and can maintain composure under pressure (Basra et al., 2016). Both terrorist groups and criminal organizations require similar resources, including false identification, fraudulent documents, transportation networks, and counter-surveillance techniques (Wang, 2010). As terrorist groups seek to maintain and increase their operational activities, their resource demands grow, necessitating collaboration with criminal networks (Phillips and Schiele, 2023). This cooperation is driven by the need for critical skills like document forgery and human smuggling, essential for sustaining terrorist activities (Phillips and Schiele, 2023).

3.3.2.2 Recruitment (how and who?)

Former criminals bring many advantages to terrorist groups such as; access to weapons through criminal networks, expertise in using forged documents, safe houses for evading authorities, excel in staying under the radar and familiarity with violence, which accelerates their involvement in terrorist activities (Basra and Neumann, 2016). Research highlights the rising presence of former criminals within terrorist cells in Europe, often named 'gangster jihadists.' These individuals bring valuable qualities to terrorist groups, such as experience with violence and clandestine behaviours (Omelicheva and Markowitz, 2021). For individuals previously involved in domestic violence, the time between joining a terrorist group and becoming involved in violence, was often extremely short, often less than four months or even just a few weeks (Basra and Neumann, 2016).

This phenomenon underscores the operational connections within the crime-terror nexus (Omelicheva and Markowitz, 2021). **The cooperation between organized crime and terrorists happens due to their shared social environments. Recruitment from these common grounds, or "melting pots," illustrates how a criminal past can contribute to radicalization processes** (Basra et al., 2016; Omelicheva and Markowitz, 2021). For individuals with prior criminal involvement, experience with violence can reduce the psychological barriers to engaging in terrorism. This familiarity with violence facilitates

quicker mobilization into extremist activities (Basra et al., 2016). The mobilization of foreign fighters for the Syrian conflict has been extraordinary, with an estimated 5,000 Western Europeans joining jihadist groups like Islamic State and Jabhat al-Nusra in 2015. This influx surpasses any previous jihadist conflict in attracting foreigners.

Alongside these foreign fighters (FTF's) are 'stay-home supporters,' who belong to the same jihadist networks but remain in their home countries. Both groups 'stay-home supporters' and 'returnee' fighters, disproportionately populated by individuals with criminal backgrounds, have been involved in numerous terrorist attacks in Europe since mid-2014 (Basra et al., 2016; Van der Veer, 2018). A critical question regarding the crime-terror nexus is how these criminal pasts contribute to radicalization (Basra et al., 2016). An example is the case of Mohammed Merah which exemplifies extreme violence preceding terrorism. Merah, responsible for killing seven people in Toulouse in 2012, had a history marked by repeated violent incidents, multiple convictions, and encounters with law enforcement from his youth. His radicalization and subsequent terrorist acts were facilitated by his established pattern of violence (Basra et al., 2016).

3.3.2.3 Prisons (where?)

Prisons are significant meeting places for individual with criminal pasts (Basra and Neumann, 2016). They are characterized by vulnerable inmates, particularly individuals who may experience **cognitive openings'; moments of personal crisis or shock that make them receptive to radical changes in beliefs and behaviours** (Basra et al., 2016). Prisons present unique sites with the seeds of future violence (Omelycheva and Markowitz, 2021). These environments facilitate the convergence of criminals and extremists, offering opportunities for radicalization and recruitment into jihadist groups (Basra and Neumann, 2016). **This process often involves a 'redemption narrative,' where prisoners seek to break from their criminal pasts and find justification in religious extremism** (Basra et al., 2016).

Prisons not only provide fertile ground for radicalization but also foster collaboration between criminals and terrorists. They enable the transfer of skills, including tactics like forging documents or accessing safe houses, which are crucial for terrorist operations (Basra and Neumann, 2016). **Prisons have the potential to institutionalize a nexus between terrorist and criminal networks, creating environments where these groups can intersect and reinforce each other's capabilities. Prisons are places where criminal and terrorist milieus converge** (Basra and Neumann, 2016). Both R3 and R4 agree with this finding. R3 questions the efficiency of prisons, noting that people are often arrested for **minor criminal activities but come out from prison radicalized. As mentioned by R4;**

The most common mode of skills transfer in my experience was direct recruitment by the terrorist organization. A terrorist group would seek to recruit and radicalize individuals who were skilled or already had a history in things like cybercrime, bank fraud, drug production.

These individuals are often recruited in prisons, or from areas where terrorists have gained control in exchange for promises of penance and redemption.

In summary, prisons represent unique sites where the vulnerabilities of inmates and the convergence of criminal and terrorist networks contribute to the spread of extremism and the enhancement of operational skills among radicalized individuals (Basra and Neumann, 2016).

3.3.3 Weak states

Beyond internal organizational factors, the broader environment is likely to influence terrorist groups' decisions to collaborate with organized crime (Phillips and Schiele, 2023). The crime-terror nexus poses an important threat to the international security. The nexus is increasingly complex and sophisticated, which is directly challenging the security of the states at national and international level (Wang, 2010). The emergence of the crime-terror nexus can be explained on the basis of two dominant paradigms; the enabling role of globalization and the permissive role of “ungoverned” and “poorly governed” territories. Academic research investigates the connections between non-state violent actors, but often overlook the direct role of the state in the relationship between terrorist groups and criminal organisations (Omelicheva and Markowitz, 2021). According to R2 and R1, due to the lack of legislation and the presence of weak investigation teams in those fragile states, the groups can seize the opportunity to operate freely. Both groups of people operate out of the law and they often take advantages of the same surroundings such as little governmental control, open borders, chaos of national boundary and dysfunction of law enforcement (Wang, 2010).

Terrorist organizations operate in various state contexts, with some trying to survive in highly capable countries with advanced security institutions, while others find it easier to function in relatively weak states (Phillips and Schiele, 2023). In highly capable states, terrorists operate with significant insecurity due to stringent government counterterrorism measures. These include surveillance of communications, infiltration of organizations, and monitoring of members by law enforcement agencies (Phillips and Schiele, 2023). Such states also have robust law enforcement, tightly controlled borders, and strong international collaboration through agencies like Europol, creating a challenging and complex operational environment for terrorist groups. Due to stringent security measures, terrorists in capable states find it difficult to conduct major criminal activities independently, such as large-scale attacks or significant logistical operations, without drawing attention. In this context, cooperating with organized crime groups can provide several advantages (Phillips and Schiele, 2023). Organized crime networks often have established methods to evade law enforcement and access resources discreetly. This can offer terrorists a more secure way to conduct operations without drawing attention. Organized crime groups possess expertise in areas like money laundering, smuggling, and forging documents, which are valuable to terrorists. They can provide these resources and skills without the terrorists needing to develop them independently. Consequently, the dynamics between

organized crime and terrorist organizations depends on the strength of the state (Phillips and Schiele, 2023).

In contrast, in weaker states with less effective governance and law enforcement, terrorists may find it easier to operate independently, conducting major crimes without as much risk of detection or interference from authorities. After the 9/11 attacks, failed states are viewed by American policy-makers as potential security threats of high order. The US President Bush's National Security Strategy report of September 2002 declares that "*America is now threatened less by conquering states than we are by failing ones*". As mentioned by Menkhaus (2019), in the research conducted by the Centre for Strategic and International Studies and the Association of the United States Army; "*One of the principal lessons of the events of September 11 is that failed states matter, not just for humanitarian reasons but for national security as well. If left unattended, such states can become sanctuaries for terrorist networks with a global reach, not to mention international organised crime and drug traffickers who can also exploit the dysfunctional environment. As such, failed states can pose a direct threat to the national interests of the United States and to the stability of entire regions.*"

Instability is in the best interest of terrorist groups because it weakens the legitimacy of the government in the eyes of the mass populations; the populations whom the terrorist groups seek to gain support from; and it is in the interest of criminal groups seeking to maximize criminal operations. (Makarenko, 2004). Convergence between organised crime and terrorism happens in weak/ fragile states and conflict-affected countries with high levels of corruption, porous borders, and ineffective law enforcement (Kulic and Bolhuis, 2023). Convergence between these groups have been especially common in Latin America, Southeast Asia, the Middle East, and Eurasia. (Makarenko, 2004). Most instances of the crime–terror nexus can be found in Afghanistan, Colombia, Iraq, Kosovo, Liberia, Nigeria, Sierra Leone, and Tajikistan, among other countries. These examples all stem from civil wars (Omelicheva and Markowitz, 2021).

Both R1 and R3 agree that non-state violent groups provide an alternative to the state. According to R1, the nexus is primarily driven by the need for funds and the presence of weak states. These two factors are central to the nexus because, in the absence of public services, terrorist groups can act with impunity and become an alternative state. This happens in the Sahel-region, but also in Iraq-Syria border with ISIS. R3 points out that states suffering from corruption, unemployment, and poverty, the population turns to terrorist organizations because they take care of their families, provide money, and offer jobs. This creates an entire system that fills the void, allowing both criminal and terrorist organizations to operate freely.

3.3.3.1 The black hole state

States that foster the convergence between transnational organised crime and terrorist groups are considered as weak/ failed states because they create safe havens for the continued operations of the convergent groups (Kulic and Bolhuis, 2023; Makarenko, 2004). Makarenko's influential research outlines a spectrum of potential terrorist-criminal interactions, ranging from cooperation to convergence into more dangerous hybrid organizations. Makarenko suggests that this convergence is more probable in weaker states (Phillips and Schiele, 2023). She speaks about the "black hole" syndrome where *the motivation of groups engaged in a civil war evolves from political to criminal and situations where a converged entity has successfully taken over control of the state, rendering it a "black hole state"* (Makarenko, 2004).

The "black hole" can occur in two contexts (Makarenko, 2004). First, the dynamics of civil wars, just like the dynamics of traditional organised crime and terrorism have changed. According to Makarenko (2004), *civil wars have evolved from wars fought for an ideology to wars hijacked by criminal interests and secured by terror actions. These wars have begun with political aims but have mutated into conflicts in which economic benefits and state control have become the priority.* An example is the civil war in Syria. The groups fighting appear to have betrayed their ideological ideals in the interest of holding on to power at whatever cost (Makarenko, 2004). Second, *in the absence of a strong state, these non-states actors are producing alternative economic and political structure. The converged criminal and terrorist groups constitute de facto governments imitating characteristics of formal state activities and replacing the state, while furthering their involvement in illegal activities* (Kulic and Bolhuis, 2023; Makarenko, 2004). Groups that thrive within 'black hole' environments are all equally motivated. They strive the 'accumulation of wealth, control of territory and people, freedom of movement and action, and legitimacy' (Makarenko, 2004).

The result of becoming a state with the "black hole" syndrome is that it challenges the legitimacy of the state (Makarenko, 2004). Respondents agree with this finding and the concept of the "black hole syndrome," *noting that it turns states into safe havens for both criminal organizations and terrorist groups.* Afghanistan has become an important safe haven with training camps for a number of terrorist groups and a strategic place for transnational criminal organisations (Makarenko, 2004). Another example is the Iraq-Syria border. This region is used as a hub for the smuggling of weapons, drugs and oil. By strengthening both their criminal and ideological political components, these actors continue to destabilize the already fragile Iraqi state (Kulic and Bolhuis, 2023). When terrorist groups are already engaged in criminal activities, they are likely to collaborate with organized crime groups. This is particularly the case for groups involved in trafficking goods or people, as they often rely on criminal networks for logistics and retail operations. Non-state violent groups that control territory can utilize it for drug cultivation and production, as well as exploit the local population through kidnapping and

extortion. Additionally, territories controlled by military groups might overlap with or be near to areas controlled by criminal organizations, necessitating some level of coordination. Therefore, territorial control is generally associated with cooperation with organized crime (Phillips and Schiele, 2023).

3.3.3.2 The state as the cause

On the other hand, many scholars argue that weak or failed states have often been seen as a product of the nexus between terrorist groups and criminal organisations, while they should be seen as a cause of the nexus (Kulic and Bolhuis, 2023; Omelicheva and Markowitz, 2021). It has been argued that the crime-terror nexus is not necessarily a result of a weak or failed state, but rather a result of the actions taken by a government seeking to capture control over illicit economy. In West Africa, for example, the appearance of the cocaine trafficking increased considerable political and financial benefits to some governments and political elites supporting the illicit trade (Omelicheva and Markowitz, 2021). In this way the state becomes a part of the nexus itself, particularly where the government and political elites are involved in illicit economic activity and security measures are used to support particular actors within the nexus (Omelicheva and Markowitz, 2021). In other words, the relation goes both ways. Weak states create safe haven for the nexus between terrorist groups and organised crime and the nexus makes a state weak and fragile.

The crime-terror nexus goes to the very heart of the relationship between the terrorist groups, organised criminal groups, and the state (Kulic and Bolhuis, 2023; Wang, 2010). The state becomes a crucial part of the nexus, not only as an environmental factor but also as an active contributor (Kulic and Bolhuis, 2023; Omelicheva and Markowitz, 2021). According to R1; the state is a contributor to the nexus, because it lets terrorist organizations operate freely. The respondent points out that; *“it should be one of the main roles of the state to take back its territory and to be closer to its population. The government should be decentralized to be closer to the population.”*

Research also shows that organised crime and terrorism cannot fully operate in totally failed states or zones of complete collapse. They require some level of transportation, banking, communication infrastructure and services. Terrorist networks have found safety in weak, but corrupted, quasi-states, like Pakistan, Yemen, Kenya, the Philippines, Guinea, Indonesia. They appear to flourish where states are governed badly rather than not at all (Menkhaus, 2006). Also, weak law enforcement, spotty border security, and higher rates of corruption are not unique to developing states. Such conditions can also exist in parts of transitional states and fully functional democracies (Omelicheva and Markowitz, 2021). This emphasizes the role of the state.

3.4 Case studies

Besides the examples mentioned throughout the literature, this section of the literature provides a brief overview of three cases where the convergence between the criminal organization and terrorist

organization happens based on the three factors; the financing of the terrorist organization through criminal activities, the skills transfer between the groups and the role of the (weak) state.

3.4.1 The Provisional Irish Republican Army (IRA)

The Provisional Irish Republican Army (IRA) serves as a classic example of a terrorist group that turned to criminal organization while maintaining its primary political objectives (Basra et al., 2016). The IRA was a militant group that aimed to separate Northern Ireland from the United Kingdom and establish a united Ireland through acts of terrorism. After the global effort to crack down on the IRA's financial networks has proved to be highly effective, the organization was forced to seek alternative funding sources. **The IRA encouraged its members to engage in criminal activities, rather than collaborating with other criminal organizations, to meet its financial needs** (Basra et al., 2016). These criminal activities included policing (enforcing their own rules in controlled areas), bank robbery, fuel laundering, and kidnapping (Wang, 2010). Despite the IRA's rare interactions with other criminal groups, there is a significant example of such cooperation. Three IRA members collaborated with FARC, sharing their expertise in bomb-making. This connection between the IRA and FARC is seen as a "one-time" partnership aimed at meeting specific objectives and operational needs (Wang, 2010). In some aspects, the IRA operated like a mafia, offering private or criminal protection to citizens in exchange for substantial financial gain. Over time, the IRA developed into a self-sufficient organization with an "in-house" capability for engaging in organized crime and minimizing the need to form alliances with other criminal groups for fundraising (Basra et al., 2016; Wang, 2010).

3.4.2 Afghanistan

The situation of the Taliban in Afghanistan is another case where a elements of terrorist organization and a criminal organization can be found. The Taliban have heavily relied on criminal networks and activities to finance their operations, such as trafficking of heroin and opium, extortion, and kidnapping for ransom (Wang, 2010). These criminal revenue streams have been crucial in sustaining their insurgency (Makarenko, 2012). Many Taliban recruits have prior criminal histories, including involvement in organized crime, drug trafficking, and other illicit activities, which have influenced their radicalization and participation in terrorist activities (Basra et al., 2016). **As the Taliban regained control of Afghanistan in 2021, they exploited the instability and lawlessness of conflict zones in Afghanistan to expand their criminal enterprises, including the illicit drug trade, smuggling, and extortion.** In April 2022, the Taliban banned opium poppy cultivation, citing religious beliefs and aiming to reduce opium's harmful effects. This led to a 95% drop in cultivation and a sharp decline in production from 6,200 to 333 tonnes within a year (Limaye, 2023). Experts believe this may reflect a strategic move by the Taliban to control the market and shift to more profitable synthetic drugs like methamphetamine (O'Donnell, 2024). Despite the ban, opium production persists, allowing the

Taliban to manipulate prices and increase profits. The ban has worsened Afghanistan's humanitarian crisis, pushing struggling farmers towards other illegal activities, potentially funding extremist groups (UNODC, 2023). This exploitation has generated significant revenue to fund their terrorist activities (Makarenko, 2012; UNODC, 2023). This highlights the critical role that the crime-terror nexus has played in the Taliban's resilience and ability to challenge both the Afghan government and international forces.

3.4.3 Iraq-Syria border

After the fall of the ISIS caliphate in Iraq and Syria, a power vacuum emerged, leading to fierce competition between ISIS remnants and Shia factions backed by Iran, including the Popular Mobilization Forces (PMF). Both criminal enterprises wanted the control over the Iraq-Syria border. This area has become a hub for the smuggling of weapons, drugs, oil, and human trafficking by both ISIS remnants and Shia PMF factions (Kulić and Bolhuis, 2023; Van der Veer, 2018). Border regions and roads leading to Baghdad are key points where these groups impose illicit taxation and extortion. **The ISIS remnants in this region function as 'hybrid criminal-political entities,' pursuing both criminal and ideological goals simultaneously** (Kulić and Bolhuis, 2023). These factions have integrated into the Iraqi state structure, blurring the lines between the state, crime, and terrorism. The competition between ISIS remnants and Shia PMF factions for control over criminal enterprises along the Iraq-Syria border has contributed to the ongoing destabilization of the already fragile Iraqi state. **By strengthening their criminal and ideological-political components, these groups continue to undermine the authority of the Iraqi government and perpetuate the cycle of violence and instability in the region.** Both entities exploit the security vacuum to engage in various illicit activities, challenging the stability of the Iraqi state (Kulić and Bolhuis, 2023).

3.5 Recommendations

3.5.1 Enhanced cooperation

As previously stated, countering terrorism and combating crime are no longer distinct activities. According to Omelicheva and Markowitz (2021), ending terrorist groups requires a range of policy instruments. This highlights the importance of enhanced cooperation between counterterrorism agents and those fighting organized crime (Philips and Schiele, 2023). Therefore, agencies responsible for both need to collaborate more systematically than before. Catherine De Bolle, Executive Director of Europol, emphasized the importance of cooperation as; *“it is the key to everything”* (De Bolle, 2024). Intelligence, law enforcement, customs, and prison authorities should institutionalize their connections, develop communication and data-sharing channels, and focus on building human capacity. This can be achieved through exchanges, joint training, and exercises, all of which help foster mutual trust and cooperation (Basra et al., 2016).

Intelligence sharing among EU member-state agencies is crucial for addressing the connections between organized crime and terrorism. Government agencies should review existing information exchange channels, extend collaboration beyond traditional partners, and adapt to the new, multi-dimensional threat. Integrating crime and terrorism databases, cross-referencing them routinely, and updating them with real-time data and digital evidence is recommended (Basra et al., 2016). At an operational level, member states must ensure that anti-crime and counter-terrorism units collaborate to identify and monitor these links (Makarenko, 2012). **Political and diplomatic considerations often hinder targeted work on the connection between OC and terrorism (Makarenko, 2012). Therefore, institutional silos need to be broken down, not only between states but also between efforts to counter crime and terrorism, or between counter-terrorism and other agencies like criminal police and customs** (Basra et al., 2016). Respondents agree with this finding that there should be “*legal harmonization between anti-crime and anti-terrorism agencies*”. The EU can play an important role here. It must lead in establishing a unified approach toward external states concerning the crime-terror nexus. The European Parliament should prompt the European Council and the European Commission to initiate the necessary actions (Makarenko, 2012).

Security agencies must extend their reach beyond their own ranks. Many crimes have local origins, and perpetrators are often known within their communities. Therefore, it is essential to raise awareness about the potential links between 'ordinary' crimes and terrorism funding and to engage local populations in prevention efforts (Basra et al., 2016). As mentioned by Annelies Verlinden, Belgian Minister of Internal Affairs it is essential to empower local authorities for closing business used for money laundering by criminal and terrorist organizations (Verlinden, 2024). This can be achieved through advertising, targeted outreach, and community policing. Building strong relationships with local authorities, who possess deeper insights into communities and local dynamics, is equally important. In return, security agencies can help alleviate local tensions, address grievances, and establish positive relationships with community leaders (Basra et al., 2016).

3.5.2 Countering financing terrorism

Terrorist operations are largely financed through criminal activities for example, credit card and insurance fraud, money laundering, and smuggling (Makarenko, 2004). Therefore, disrupting these financial streams is crucial. **If authorities cannot disarm a terrorist group, they can aim to weaken it by cutting off its funding and resource channels** (Phillips and Schiele, 2023). It's important to focus not only on international financial sources but also on smaller-scale funding. Many terrorist attacks have been carried out with minimal financial resources, so a comprehensive approach to combating terrorist financing is necessary (Basra et al., 2016). Efforts to counter terrorist financing should include all potential funding sources, including small-scale and petty crimes such as drug dealing, theft, robbery, and the trade in counterfeit goods like clothes, bags, watches, cigarettes, electronics, and computer

games (Basra et al. 2016; Makarenko, 2012). This approach not only disrupts terrorist financing but also reduces ordinary crimes (Basra et al., 2016). Respondents agree with the finding that funding for terrorism must be tackled. However, R1 comments that it is difficult due to a lack of resources and weak investigation teams. Therefore, we must invest in more robust investigation teams and human resources to combat money laundering and other criminal finances.

The private banking sector plays an important role in this fight. Banks are often affected by crimes such as smuggling, fraud, forgeries, and intellectual property infringements. They have a commercial interest in countering these crimes and can provide valuable information to law enforcement agencies. However, there is limited understanding or awareness among European officials and policymakers about the role of public-private partnerships (Basra et al., 2016). Many security agencies struggle to collaborate with businesses or understand their role in combating crime and terrorism. There are also few examples or best practices to reference (Basra et al., 2016). Collaboration with the private sector, particularly the financial industry, is essential in fighting organized crime and terrorist financing by detecting and reporting fraud, money laundering, and other suspicious activities. The financial sector should work more closely with government agencies to identify regulatory gaps and implement innovative solutions (Makarenko, 2012). However, a critique by Omelicheva and Markowitz (2021) suggests that reducing a terrorist organization's funding does not immediately ensure the group's collapse.

3.5.3 Research on the state's role

Since this research also examines the role of the state, it highlights its crucial involvement in the crime-terror nexus. Future research is needed to understand the different roles of the state, including state-sponsorship, and their impact on the crime-terror nexus dynamics (Kulic and Bolhuis, 2023). R3 adds that research on the state must originate from the state itself. *"The state must be aware and willing to tackle the problem. There is a need for a multifaceted approach that must come from the governments themselves. They must be willing to tackle this problem and ask for help. We cannot invade a country like that; the sovereignty of the state must be respected. Every state is unique and requires a specific approach."* Instead of looking at the state through the lens of strength or weakness, it is more productive to look at the different modes of collaboration and confrontation between the state, organised crime and other non-state violent actors (Omelicheva and Markowitz; 2021). One can consider whether state weakness engenders the criminal-terrorist convergence or results from it (Omelicheva and Markowitz; 2021). There is also the need for a model around the different roles of the state. This model would help to have a clear distinction between violent state-embedded actors and entities without state connections (Kulic and Bolhuis, 2023). This model would be applicable on the situation on the ground to make the differentiation between state funding and revenues from organised crime clearer (Kulic and Bolhuis, 2023).

3.5.4 Criminality as the main factor

While most member states have focused primarily on terrorist financing, law enforcement agencies need to broaden their investigations to uncover links beyond the obvious criminal connections. Currently, many EU member states have a fragmented understanding of OC and terrorism (Makarenko, 2012). However, one thing is clear is that both organized crime and terrorist organizations share the same factor, which is *criminality*. If we look at the crime-terror continuum designed by Makarenko, one consistent and easily identifiable factor is “criminality”. Regardless of where a group sits along the continuum, every point indicates some degree of involvement in criminal activities (Makarenko, 2004). According to R2, everything starts with legislation: We need changes in the legislation, and we need to build the capacity to recognize the crimes of the nexus.’ According to Makarenko, focusing on criminal activity has been under-utilized in formulating policy responses to terrorism (Makarenko, 2004). Law enforcement needs to keep an eye on links between terrorists and criminals, but it also should not forget about terrorists engaging in crime on their own (Phillips and Schiele, 2023). Although it is important to understand the political motivations of terrorist groups, counter-terrorism policies should focus on the criminal aspects of the groups to achieve greater success in weakening them (Makarenko, 2004; Van der Wilt and Paulussen, 2019).

4 Conclusion

The study aims to explore the dynamics of the crime-terror nexus, focusing on the financing of terrorism through criminal activities, the transfer of skills between groups, and the role of weak states. The research is based on a qualitative, mixed-methods approach, combining an extensive literature review of academic and governmental sources with four expert interviews. The main research question guiding the study is: "What are the factors that contribute to the crime-terror nexus?" This question is further divided into three sub-questions, each addressing one of the key factors. In this section of the master's thesis, an effort is made to answer the research question. First, a brief conclusion is provided on the concept of the crime-terror nexus, followed by conclusions that align with the order of the research questions.

4.1 Conclusion on the concept crime-terror nexus

Traditionally, organized crime and terrorism were seen as distinct, with the former focused on profit and the latter on ideological or political goals. The concept of the "crime-terror nexus" refers to the blurred lines between organized crime and terrorism, where the two phenomena overlap in both objectives and activities. However, this clear-cut distinction has become less applicable as more groups have begun to engage in both criminal and terrorist activities, often for mutual benefit.

This nexus is not a new concept, having been discussed since the 1980s, but it has gained more attention in recent years due to the growing number of groups that display characteristics of both organized crime and terrorism. These groups may shift between or combine criminal and terrorist activities depending on their environment and objectives, making it difficult to maintain a strict separation between the two. This fluid relationship is captured by Tamara Makarenko's "crime-terror continuum," which illustrates how groups can evolve along a spectrum, from purely criminal to purely terrorist activities, often converging into entities that pursue both political and financial goals simultaneously. Additionally, the respondents interviewed for the study have generally shown more familiarity with the "crime-terror continuum" than with the traditional "profit-ideology dichotomy."

Despite the recognition of the crime-terror nexus by international bodies such as the UN, which has expressed concern over the connections between terrorism and transnational organized crime, the concept itself suffers from a lack of clear conceptualization. Scholars and practitioners often struggle to define the nexus precisely, leading to confusion and sometimes criticism for being overly broad. This lack of conceptual clarity complicates efforts to distinguish between criminal and terrorist activities, potentially hindering law enforcement's ability to apply appropriate legal frameworks.

4.2 Conclusion on the factors that contribute to the nexus

4.2.1 The factor: financing terrorism

Answer to the research question: How does the financing of terrorism through criminal activities contribute to the crime-terror nexus?

As state sponsorship has declined, many terrorist groups have more and more relied on criminal activities as alternative funding sources. This shift is essential for sustaining their operations, particularly as some evolve into quasi-states or insurgent armies, necessitating substantial and continuous financial resources. As stated by the respondents engaging in such activities is essential for the survival of the terrorist groups.

Moreover, the nexus is reinforced by the operational familiarity of individuals with criminal backgrounds who reuse their illicit activities to finance terrorism. This continuity in behaviour complicates the detection and prevention efforts of law enforcement, as it becomes challenging to separate funds used for terrorism from those used for other criminal purposes. Additionally, the collaboration between terrorist organizations and organized criminal groups offers mutual benefits, enhancing the durability and effectiveness of both. Terrorist groups gain a steady flow of funds, while criminal organizations benefit from the instability and weakened law enforcement that often accompanies terrorist activity. This relationship strengthens the terrorist groups, making them more resilient and dangerous.

Also as mentioned by the respondents, terrorist organizations demonstrate a remarkable ability to adapt to their environments by exploiting the criminal opportunities available in the regions where they operate. For instance, ISIS has capitalized on the illicit trade of archaeological artifacts in areas under its control, while other groups, like the Taliban and FARC, have engaged in drug trafficking in regions where such activities thrive. This adaptability highlights the fluid and dynamic nature of the crime-terror nexus, as terrorist organizations continue to evolve and integrate criminality into their funding strategies.

The financing of terrorism through criminal activities plays thus a crucial role in the crime-terror nexus. The convergence between terrorism and criminal activities, such as the self-financing of attacks and other illicit methods, not only sustains terrorist groups but also makes it more challenging to fight both crime and terrorism. As these two groups become more intertwined, the traditional understanding of terrorist financing is challenged, necessitating more sophisticated approaches to counter this growing threat.

4.2.2 The factor: skills transfer

Answer to the research question: How does the transfer of skills between groups contribute to the crime-terror nexus?

The transfer of skills between criminal and terrorist groups reinforces the crime-terror nexus. This transfer occurs through operational support, recruitment, and the shared environments where these groups interact, such as prisons. Terrorist groups gain operational support from criminal networks, which often possess specialized skills like document forgery, access to safe houses, and the ability to evade law enforcement. These capabilities are crucial for terrorists, enabling them to carry out more sophisticated and deadly attacks with reduced risk. A finding that is also shared among the respondents.

Instead of developing these skills internally, terrorist groups frequently outsource them to criminal experts, as exemplified by the Paris attacks in 2015, where former criminals with ties to organized crime were involved in obtaining fake IDs. This outsourcing not only makes terrorist operations more efficient but also minimizes exposure to risk in areas where the terrorist group lacks expertise, such as money laundering or narcotics trafficking.

The recruitment of individuals with criminal backgrounds further intensifies this nexus. Former criminals bring valuable expertise in violence, clandestine operations, and dealing with law enforcement, which are all assets in the execution of terrorist activities. The increasing presence of these "gangster jihadists" within terrorist cells highlights how criminal experience can accelerate involvement in terrorism, reducing the psychological barriers to committing acts of violence and facilitating quicker mobilization into extremist activities.

Prisons play a critical role in this skills transfer, serving as meeting points where criminals and potential terrorists can interact and collaborate. In these environments, individuals with criminal pasts are particularly vulnerable to radicalization, often seeking redemption through extremist ideologies. This convergence not only fosters radicalization but also allows for the transfer of essential operational skills that are later used in terrorist activities. Prisons therefore serve as breeding grounds for the crime-terror nexus, institutionalizing the relationships between criminal and terrorist networks while enhancing their shared expertise.

4.2.3 The factor: weak states

Answer to the research question: How does the state play a role in contributing to the crime-terror nexus?

The state plays a crucial role in contributing to the crime-terror nexus, particularly through its weaknesses and governance failures. In weak or failed states, where government control is limited, law enforcement is ineffective, and corruption is widespread, both terrorist and organized crime groups find fertile ground to operate. These states often serve as safe havens, providing a permissive environment where the nexus between crime and terror can thrive with minimal interference from authorities. For instance, in regions like the Iraq-Syria border, the lack of strong state control has allowed both terrorist and criminal organizations to collaborate closely, engaging in activities such as smuggling and trafficking, which further destabilize these regions and undermine state authority.

Moreover, the concept of the "black hole" state illustrates how the convergence of terrorist and criminal organizations can lead to the creation of de facto governments within these weak states. These converged groups often mimic state characteristics, controlling territory, resources, and even populations, while continuing their illicit activities. This not only challenges the legitimacy of the official state but also reinforces the power of these hybrid groups, making it even more difficult for the state to regain control.

On the other hand, the state's role is not limited to being a passive setting for the crime-terror nexus. In some cases, the state itself can become an active contributor to this nexus, particularly when political elites and government officials are involved in or benefit from illicit economic activities. This can be seen in certain regions of West Africa, where state actors have been implicated in facilitating drug trafficking for personal or political gain. In such scenarios, the state becomes part of the problem, perpetuating the nexus rather than addressing it.

In summary, the state's contribution to the crime-terror nexus is double. Weak and poorly governed states provide an environment where this nexus can flourish, while in some cases, the state actively participates in or even drives the nexus through corruption and involvement in illicit activities. A finding that is strongly shared among the respondents pointing out the role and responsibility of the state.

4.3 Conclusion on the recommendations

Tackling the factors contributing to the crime-terror nexus requires a multi-faceted approach involving enhanced cooperation, countering terrorist financing, research on the state's role, and focusing on criminality as a central issue.

First, the importance of **enhanced cooperation** between agencies. Agencies responsible for counterterrorism and combating organized crime must work together, breaking down institutional silos that often hinder effective action. This collaboration should extend beyond traditional partners to include intelligence, law enforcement, customs, and prison authorities, all of whom must institutionalize their connections and develop robust communication and data-sharing channels. Joint training, exchanges, and exercises are crucial for fostering mutual trust and improving operational efficiency. Additionally, intelligence sharing among EU member-state agencies is vital for addressing the links between organized crime and terrorism. Integrating crime and terrorism databases, routinely cross-referencing them, and updating them with real-time data is recommended to ensure a comprehensive approach to these complex threats.

Furthermore, local authorities and communities play a crucial role in preventing crime and terrorism. Raising awareness about the potential links between ordinary crimes and terrorism funding, and empowering local authorities to take action against money laundering and other illicit activities, can significantly contribute to address these threats. Engaging communities through targeted outreach, advertising, and community policing can also help build strong relationships between security agencies and local populations, making it easier to identify and address potential risks.

In addition to enhanced cooperation, **countering the financing of terrorism** is essential. Terrorist operations are often funded through criminal activities such as money laundering, fraud, and smuggling. Disrupting these financial streams is crucial for weakening terrorist groups. This requires a comprehensive approach that targets not only large-scale funding sources but also smaller-scale activities, including petty crimes that contribute to terrorism financing. Collaboration with the private banking sector is also important in this fight. Banks, affected by crimes like smuggling and fraud, can provide valuable information to law enforcement agencies. However, there is a need for greater awareness and understanding among policymakers about the role of public-private partnerships in combating crime and terrorism.

Research on the state's role in the crime-terror nexus is another critical area. Understanding the various roles of the state, including state sponsorship and how weak governance contributes to the nexus, is necessary for developing effective counter-strategies. Future research should focus on creating a model that distinguishes between violent state-embedded actors and entities without state

connections, helping to clarify the relationship between state weakness and criminal-terrorist convergence.

Finally, while most efforts have focused on terrorist financing, it is essential to broaden investigations to uncover deeper links between organized crime and terrorism. Law enforcement agencies need to pay closer attention to the **criminal activities of terrorist groups**, as criminality is a consistent factor across the crime-terror continuum. By focusing on the criminal aspects of terrorist groups, counter-terrorism policies can achieve greater success in weakening these organizations. This approach requires changes in legislation, as well as building the capacity to recognize and address the crimes that contribute to the crime-terror nexus.

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6 Attachments

Attachment 1: Coding scheme

A. HISTORY

1. Cold war → collapse Soviet Union and decline state sponsorship
2. 9/11 → global war on terror

B. DEFINITIONS

1. Terrorism
2. Organized crime
3. Narco-terrorism
4. The concept “crime-terror nexus”
 - i. The profit-ideology dichotomy
 - ii. The crime-terror continuum → Tamara Makarenko

C. THE FACTORS ON THE CRIME-TERROR NEXUS

1. Financing terrorism → drug trade
2. Skills transfer
 - i. Operational support: the what?
 - ii. Recruitment: the how and who?
 - iii. Prisons: the where?
3. Weak states
 - i. The black hole state → Tamara Makarenko
 - ii. The state as the cause

D. CASE STUDIES

1. IRA (Irish Republican Army)
2. Taliban
3. Iraq-Syria border

E. RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Enhanced cooperation
2. Countering financing terrorism
3. Research on the state’s role
4. Criminality as the main factor

Attachment 2: Interview guide

Introduction

Dear (name),

My name is Randa Kandrouch. I am a master's student in International Politics at the CERIS Diplomatic School of Brussels. As part of my master's thesis, I'm conducting research on the factors contributing to the crime-terror nexus. The starting hypothesis of my research is that the emergence of the crime-terror nexus can be explained by two paradigms: the enabling role of globalization and the permissive role of weak states (Omelicheva & Markowitz, 2021). These two paradigms are further broken down into specific factors contributing to the crime-terror nexus:

- **The financing of terrorism:** Criminal organizations provide terrorists with necessary funds through activities such as drug trafficking. Additionally, terrorist organizations may engage in the drug trade to raise funds for their activities (Omelicheva and Markowitz, 2021; INCB, 2021; Makarenko, 2004).
- **The transfer of skills:** The skills that are exchanged between the groups are further divided into three questions: what skills are transferred (skills for operational support), how and by whom the skills are carried out (through recruitment of people with a criminal past), and where does the transfer happen (in prisons).
- **Weak states:** This involves the analysis of the "black hole syndrome" (Makarenko, 2004) and the state's role in providing a safe haven for criminal and terrorist organizations to operate (Omelicheva and Markowitz, 2021; Kulic and Bolhuis, 2023).

The interview will last approximately 45 minutes to 1 hour. Everything said during the interview will be treated in a confidential and anonymous manner. I'm not recording the interview, only taking notes. No personal information is mentioned in the master's thesis.

Do you have any questions or comments before we start?

General information

I will first start with a number of general questions to have some background information about you.

1. What is your profession/ expertise?
2. What is your motivation for participating in this interview?

We will now go into the actual questions of the interview. First, we will discuss the different concepts and then we will go into the different factors.

Understanding terrorism, organised crime and narco-terrorism

We're going to start with how you define the different concepts. The concept "crime-terror" will be divided in "organized crime" and "terrorism".

3. How would you define terrorism?
 - a. *The key components of this definition include (1) the use of violence, (2) the pursuit of political or social goals, and (3) the aim to intimidate a wider audience*
4. How would you define organised crime?
 - a. *"A group of three or more individuals existing for some time, working together to commit crimes for financial or material gain".*
 - b. *"A continuing criminal enterprise that rationally works to profit from illicit activities that are often in great public demand. Its continuing existence is maintained through corruption of public officials and the use of intimidation, threats or force to protect its operations".*
5. How would you define narco-terrorism? (vs. crime-terror nexus)
 - a. *Do you think it is the same?*
 - b. *Can it be used to explain the nexus according to you?*

The concept "crime-terror nexus"

6. How would you define the crime-terror nexus?
 - a. *Lack of conceptualization*
7. Have you heard of the profit-ideology dichotomy? (in this context)
 - a. *Yes/No: if no, give explanation.*
 - b. *Do you think it is the appropriate way to approach the nexus?*
 - c. *Crime is seen as a profit-maximizing, non-politically and non-ideologically motivated phenomenon, and terrorism as strictly ideologically motivated phenomenon, without any profit driven actions.*
8. Have you heard of the crime-terror continuum? (by Makarenko)
 - a. *Yes/No: if no, give explanation.*
 - b. *Do you think it is the appropriate way to approach the nexus?*
 - c. *The continuum illustrates how "a single group can slide up and down the scale, between the traditionally called organised crime and terrorism, depending on the environment in which it operates"*
 - d. *A **tactical relationship** means a one-spot or short timeframe cooperation without any complementary enduring goals*
 - e. *A **strategic alliance** between organised crime groups and terrorists is based on their consistent interests and aim to achieve mutual expectations of long-term goals*

- f. The **convergence** can take place in two modes. On the one hand we have the criminal groups that display political motivations. On the other hand, we have terrorist groups that were initially ideology driven, change into criminal enterprises using political rhetoric as a façade for perpetrating criminal activities.

We will now discuss the factors contributing to the crime-terror nexus. We will discuss the financing of terrorism, the skills transfer and the role of weak states.

Financing terrorism

9. How do you perceive the relationship between criminal activities and the financing of terrorist organizations? Could you elaborate on the significance of this relationship?
- The funding of terrorism can be separated into two categories: the funding of the organizations itself (big amount for ISIS, IRA etc.) and the funding of the attacks (small amount like the attacks of Paris November 2015 etc.)*
 - According to you what is the role of petty crime in financing terrorism?*
10. Which criminal activity do you believe are most commonly utilized by terrorist organizations for funding, and why?
- Drug trade → Why drug trade?*
11. What are the primary motivations for terrorist organizations to engage in criminal activities? Could you provide examples if possible?
- On the one hand, by consolidating the financial base of terrorist groups, organised criminal groups make terrorist organisations more durable and deadly (Omelicheva and Markowitz, 2021).*
 - On the other side, acting alongside a terrorist organization that controls a territory, organised criminal groups, can gain in their ability to move free of the government's detection (Omelicheva and Markowitz, 2021).*
12. Can you provide any case studies or specific examples where criminal activities have significantly financed terrorism?

The skills transfer

13. In your experience, how common is the transfer of skills between organized crime groups and terrorist organizations?
14. What types of skills are most commonly transferred between these groups, and how do these skills enhance the capabilities of terrorist organizations?
- Operational support: safe houses, forging documents, weapons etc.*

- b. Recruitment: criminal past enhances the chance of conducting terrorist attacks*
 - c. Prisons: radicalization + transfer skills = institutionalize the nexus*
15. According to you what motivates organized crime groups and terrorist organizations to share skills and expertise? Could you elaborate on the driving factors behind this collaboration?
16. Can you provide specific examples or case studies where skill transfer has notably enhanced the capabilities of terrorist groups?

Weak states

17. According to you what is the difference between operating in a “highly capable state” vs. a “weak state” for criminal organizations and terrorist organizations?
18. To what extent do you believe weak states and post-conflict territories contribute to the crime-terror nexus? Could you provide detailed reasons for your perspective?
- a. Have you heard of the black hole syndrome? Yes/No. If no give explanation*
 - b. Black hole syndrome: where the convergence happens*
 - i. First, the dynamics of civil wars have changed. These wars have begun with political aims but have mutated into conflicts in which economic benefits and state control have become the priority*
 - ii. Second, in the absence of a strong state, these non-states actors are producing alternative economic and political structure.*
 - iii. → Result: both have the same motivation, which is; accumulation of power*
 - iv. → Result: the state becomes a black hole*
19. What characteristics of weak states make them particularly vulnerable to the convergence of crime and terrorism?
- a. Post-conflict*
 - b. Corrupt governments*
 - c. Do you think weak states create safe havens for the nexus, or the nexus makes a state weak? According to you what role does the state play? A victim? Or a contributor?*
20. Can you provide examples of regions or countries where the crime-terror nexus is particularly prominent due to weak state conditions or post-conflict environments?

Recommendations

21. What measures do you believe are most effective to tackle the crime-terror nexus? Could you elaborate on why these measures are effective?

a. Enhanced cooperation

i. Cooperation with “weak states” to get information, but how valid is that information? Were human rights respected to get that information?

ii. Some countries may see information sharing as a violation on its sovereignty, how to manage that?

b. Countering financing terrorism

i. Should there be more cooperation with the banking sector? What about the privacy of the consumer?

c. Research on the state’s role

d. Criminality as the main factor

22. What are the biggest challenges in implementing these measures to combat the crime-terror nexus?

23. Do you have any additional comments or recommendations regarding the crime-terror nexus?

Conclusion

We have now come to the end of the interview. Do you have any questions or comments? (Yes/ No). I would like to emphasize that I treat the data in an anonymous and confidential manner. If you are interested in the results, I can certainly send them to you later.

I would like to thank you again for your participation in my master's thesis.